

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE XI

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

November 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

Q @pinagpalapublishingservices **Search**

Q pinagpala_publishing **Search**

Q www.pinagpalapublishing.com **Search**

INFLUENCE OF FAMILY SUPPORT AND PEER NETWORKS ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF LEARNERS: INPUTS FOR A STRENGTHENED HOMEROOM PARENT-TEACHER PROGRAM

Marjorie Joanna R. Dalimot¹, Eric G. Teñoso²
¹Palar Integrated School, Taguig City, Philippines
²National Teachers College, Manila City, Philippines

Keywords: Family Support, Peer Networks, Academic Achievement, Parental Involvement, Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program, Learners' Performance

ABSTRACT

The Philippines' low global education ranking (Manila Times, 2022) highlights the urgent need for evidence-based strategies to improve student learning. This study examines how family support and peer networks influence learners' academic achievement to enhance the effectiveness of the Parent-Teacher Program. Using an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design, data were collected from 263 survey respondents and 15 interviewees. Findings show that parental support, characterized by emotional stability, motivation, and guidance, significantly improves academic performance. Positive peer relationships also promote collaboration, shared learning, and encouragement. Conversely, insufficient emotional support and negative peer influence diminish motivation and achievement. Grounded in Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, the study shows that both family and peers constitute the microsystem shaping student development. These findings highlight the need for a strengthened Parent-Teacher Program that fosters genuine collaboration between home and school, enabling parents and teachers to cultivate supportive learning environments.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rise of digital media, social networking, and mobile gadgets, learners today are more connected than ever—both online and in person. Filipino learners show diverse learning styles shaped by their identities and experiences in this tech-driven world. However, international assessments have placed their performance among the lowest globally (Haw & King, 2023). The PISA (2022) report and OECD findings emphasize that strong parental support was vital for students' learning and well-being, while the Department of Education (2019) highlighted the importance of positive peer relationships.

Guided by these insights and observations from Palar Integrated School, this study explores how family and peer support influence the academic achievement of Grade 9 and 10 learners. Using a mixed-method approach, surveys and interviews with students, parents, and teachers revealed how these relationships shape motivation, study habits, and goal setting. The results guided the creation of a Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program designed to strengthen collaboration between home and school, fostering environments that support every learner's growth and achievement.

Background of the Study

Academic achievement is not solely a product of classroom instruction, it is also influenced by a learner's social environment, particularly family support and peer networks. Family involvement provides emotional stability, motivation, and reinforcement of learning values, while peer networks contribute to academic habits, study behaviors, and social integration. Despite their critical roles, these influences are often underutilized in school support programs.

Adolescents aged 14-16 are in critical period of development. This stage, begin to form stronger peer relationships and increasingly seek independence from families. There is also an increase in academic demands and performance during this period which begins to influence future educational paths. Learners at this age tend

to be more articulate about emotional and social support they receive from family and peers. Hence, the researcher included Grades 9 and 10 in this study as they are the ones belonging to this developmental period.

This study recognizes how family and peer dynamics impact learners' academic performance. By examining these relationships, the research aims to generate practical insights that can inform and enhance the Homeroom Parent- Teacher Program. It seeks to Strengthen this program with evidence-based strategies that foster more meaningful engagement between families, teachers, and peer groups, ultimately contributing to improved academic outcomes.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The influence of family support and peer networks on students' learning development has received extensive attention from educational researchers. This review covers relevant research and theories that illustrate how these components interconnect and establish the foundation for the present study.

Academic Achievement in the Post-Pandemic Age

Academic achievement refers to the level of success a learner attains in school, often measured through grades, test scores, and completed coursework (Board, 2022). In the post-pandemic era, global changes have reshaped what academic success means. Learners today must not only master basic literacy but also develop digital skills, adaptability, and creativity (Wei, 2023). Studies show that being adaptable and using technology effectively improves student engagement and learning outcomes (Martin et al., 2021).

During the pandemic, learning expectations shifted dramatically. Motz et al. (2021) found that students had more assignments in online classes, but many felt less successful and achieved lower grades because much of the work lacked real learning value. Motivation remains an important factor in academic success since it drives persistence and goal achievement (Steinmayr et al., 2019; Lo et al., 2022). Nurhopipah et al. (2021) found that family involvement and religious activities continued to support students' learning motivation, even when it had a direct effect on decreased in GPA. Meanwhile, Carredo et al. (2022) discovered no strong link between motivation and study habits during the pandemic, though gender appeared to influence motivation levels.

As schools reopened, many adopted hybrid learning. Jihan et al. (2023) found that flexible and inclusive teaching strategies improved student participation and academic performance. Overall, post-pandemic academic achievement goes beyond grades. It now includes digital literacy, emotional resilience, and adaptability. Schools must continue to support inclusive and holistic approaches that help learners succeed in a fast-changing, technology-driven world.

Family Support for Gen Z Adolescents and Academic Achievement

Family support plays a vital role in the holistic development of Generation Z adolescents. The American Psychological Association (2022) emphasizes that parents help their children navigate digital challenges by fostering open communication, emotional support, and strong values. For Gen Z, who are deeply connected to technology and social media, family guidance is crucial for balancing online and offline life and promoting well-being and academic success. Sharma et al. (2023) highlight that family relationships greatly influence a child's overall health and development, regardless of culture. In modern societies, family interaction is seen as a continuous process shaped by social behavior and shared meaning. Understanding these changing family dynamics helps explain how parents of Generation Z function in today's context. During the pandemic, Balayar and Langlais (2021) found that parents devoted more time to supporting their children's remote learning, which improved motivation and emotional well-being but reduced social interaction and academic performance. Similarly, Kirsch and Vaiouli (2023) revealed that adolescents found home learning more tiring and less engaging, with prior performance and adult support being key predictors of success. Agostinelli et al. (2022) showed that the pandemic worsened educational inequality, especially for low-income families with limited time and resources for home learning. Peer interactions also played a major role in students' academic performance. Meanwhile, Zafirah et al. (2021) found no direct link between family support and learning achievement during distance education, suggesting that other factors may influence outcomes.

On the other hand, Mau Kasi et al. (2021) reported that active parental involvement—helping with homework and school activities—positively affected students' academic performance. These mixed findings suggest that the impact of family support on learning depends on social and cultural contexts, highlighting the need for continued research in this area.

Peer Networks and Academic Achievement

Peer networks play a vital role in the academic and social lives of Generation Z students. In today's digital age, these networks go beyond classrooms, shaping communication, collaboration, and identity formation through social media and online interactions (Burgess, 2021; Schwieger & Ladwig, 2018).

Brouwer and Engels (2021) emphasized that friendships within peer networks provide emotional stability, a sense of belonging, and support for academic and social adjustment. Students who lack strong peer connections are more likely to feel isolated and disengaged, which may lead to poor academic outcomes. Their study also highlighted that peer serve as important sources of academic help, and the way students seek or offer assistance can influence both social acceptance and learning success.

Similarly, Berthelon et al. (2019) found that the quality, size, and cohesiveness of study groups significantly affect student performance—students with supportive and high-achieving peers tend to perform better.

During the pandemic, peer networks became even more essential. They provided emotional and academic support, helping students cope with isolation and remote learning challenges. Koele et al. (2023) reported that students with positive and supportive friendships experienced fewer emotional problems and better academic outcomes throughout the pandemic.

In summary, strong and positive peer networks foster academic success, emotional well-being, and social belonging. They are not just a source of friendship but a foundation for learning, resilience, and personal growth among Gen Z students.

Synthesis

The review of literature shows that both family support and peer networks greatly influence learners' academic achievement. Parental involvement—through emotional support, guidance, and participation in school activities—consistently improves students' performance. Likewise, positive peer relationships encourage collaboration, motivation, and school engagement. However, findings differ on the extent of peer influence. While supportive peer groups enhance achievement, negative peer pressure can lead to distraction and lower academic focus, especially among adolescents.

Some studies also suggest that family support may not always have a direct effect on grades but can improve students' confidence and engagement, which in turn boosts achievement. A key gap identified is the limited exploration of programs that connect families, peers, and schools—such as the Homeroom Parent-Teacher program. Few studies examine how these collaborations can strengthen student outcomes.

This study aims to address that gap by analyzing how family and peer support interact within the school environment. It also proposes ways to enhance the Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program to promote stronger partnerships among parents, teachers, and students. By doing so, it supports more unified, data-driven, and collaborative approaches to improving learner development.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1

The Ecological Systems Theory by Bronfenbrenner is a developmental psychology framework that investigates how people are affected over time by their local and global environments. This theory, which was created by Urie Bronfenbrenner, highlights the intricate social systems in which people participate. The theory is composed of multiple nested environmental systems, each with unique dynamics and effects on the development of an individual (Guy-Evans, 2022).

Peer Networks are situated in the microsystem but interact dynamically across all ecological levels. Understanding their role through this theory helps educational leaders and teachers create environments where positive peer influence is encouraged, and harmful dynamics are mitigated through structured programs like Homeroom Parent– Teacher Program.

According to Guy-Evans (2022) in their analysis of the classroom implications of the theory, to support the development of ecological systems in educational practice, the theory states that parents and teachers should cooperate and have open lines of communication to effectively meet the child's needs. Instructors ought to be aware of the circumstances that their students' families may be experiencing, including social and economic conditions within various systems. The microsystem includes the environments where a child has direct, face-to-face interactions—such as home, school, and peer groups.

According to the theory, a good relationship between parents and teachers should positively influence a child's development. The parents also need to take a crucial role in their children's academic and social development. To promote positive development, they must work together with their peers and take part in worthwhile learning activities (Guy-Evans, 2022). On the other hand, peer networks may both positively and negatively influence development. Positive peer relationships can enhance motivation, self-esteem, and engagement in school. Negative peer influences (e.g., peer pressure, bullying) can lead to maladaptive behavior or academic disengagement.

This theory was therefore deemed appropriate for this research investigation conducted through this research. It highlights the interplay of the different systems and how academic achievement could best be attained the learners.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory explains how a person's development is shaped by different environmental systems, from immediate settings like home and school to larger social influences (Guy-Evans, 2022). Within this framework, peer networks belong to the microsystem, where direct interactions occur, but their effects extend across all levels of a learner's environment.

In education, the theory emphasizes strong collaboration between parents and teachers to support students' growth. Open communication and understanding of family and social conditions help create supportive learning environments. Positive relationships with peers can boost motivation, confidence, and academic engagement, while negative influences such as peer pressure or bullying can hinder learning.

This theory is relevant to the present study as it illustrates how family, peers, and school systems interact to shape learners' academic achievement. It supports the idea that effective collaboration among these

systems—through programs like the Homeroom Parent-Teacher initiative—can enhance student development and success.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the influence of microsystem factors of family and peers as described by Bronfenbrenner (1977) on the academic achievement of Junior High School learners. Specifically, the following questions were investigated:

1. What is the level of academic achievement of the participants?
2. What is the participants' perceived level of family support?
3. What is the extent of peer networks and interactions of the respondents?
4. Do levels of family support and peer networks have a significant relationship with the academic achievement of Junior High School Learners?
5. How are family support and peer networks and interaction practices experienced by the participants in line with their academic achievement?
6. Based on the data, what findings can be drawn for a proposed Strengthened the Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program?

Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between family support and peer networks with the academic achievement of Junior High School learners.

Significance of the Study

The researcher believes this study would create data that would aid the following groups:

Students. This study will assist the students in shaping their behavior and becoming positive influences in their classmates by performing academically. Proper counsel will help them reach their goals and become the best version of themselves.

Teachers. This study will assist teachers in strengthening their teaching techniques and strategies to determine the learning needs of their students.

Parents. This study will help parents and guardians become more aware of the importance of their guidance in their children's development.

School Administrators. This study will provide valuable insights that enable administrators to develop more targeted interventions and policies that foster a supportive learning environment both in school and at home, promoting strong collaboration between families, peers, and educators.

Educational Management Students. This empowers Educational Management Students to adopt a system-thinking mindset, recognizing the complex interplay of factors influencing learners' success and equipping them to design strategic, collaborative, and evidence – based solutions in school settings.

Future Researchers. This study may also serve as a reference for other scholars and researchers interested in conducting further studies to expand knowledge on this topic.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

Grade 9 and 10 students are at a critical stage as they transition from junior to senior high school. This period brings greater academic challenges, social pressure, and a stronger need for emotional support. At this stage, the influence of family support and peer networks becomes more evident as students gain independence and form deeper social connections.

The study focused on Grade 9 and 10 students from various sections of Palar Integrated School to capture diverse experiences and perspectives. This provided a well-rounded understanding of how family involvement and peer interactions affect academic performance. However, since the research was conducted in a specific school setting, the findings may not fully represent students from other cultural or educational contexts.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Data were gathered through self-reported surveys and interviews, which may include biases related to memory or social desirability. Factors such as socioeconomic status and cognitive differences were beyond the study's scope. Despite these limitations, the research offers valuable insights into how family and peer support shape learners' academic success.

The findings serve as a foundation for developing a strengthened Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program aimed at improving collaboration between parents and educators to better support students' learning and overall development.

3. METHODOLOGY

This stage intends to apply the analytical technique to analyze the link across family support, peer networks, and students' academic achievement. By studying these features, useful insights guided the creation of a Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program. This initiative aims to build a combined effort among educators and parents to promote a support system to increase children's academic progress. This phase describes how this academic endeavor was carried out. It also describes the sample, data-collection strategies, data-analysis procedures and ethical consideration.

Research Design

The researcher used an explanatory sequential research design. It was a mixed- method research design which focuses on quantitative phase, followed by a qualitative phase (Creswell, 2011). It occurred in two different interactive stages, starting with the collection and analysis of the quantitative data outcomes followed by a qualitative phase informed by quantitative findings (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018; Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017; Shorten & Smith, 2017; Wisdom & Creswell, 2013). This research method was suitable for studying to determine the extent to which family support and peer networks influenced academic achievement. As the study focused on an analysis of factors, in-depth processing of data came from the data sets to be able to identify inputs for the strengthened Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program. Priya (2021) emphasized that in using the approach the researcher was free to use whatever data collection technique that best served their objectives, given the technique was practical and moral. Generally, a variety of data collecting procedures, including questionnaires, surveys, in-depth interviews, participant/non-participant observation, and document analysis, were used to gather data for a sound, unadulterated, and unbiased examination of the phenomenon under research (Priya, 2021).

Participants

Table 1

Distribution of participants from grades 9 and 10 for sampling of the study

Grade 9 sections	Number of Participants	Grade 10 sections	Number of Participants	Total number of participants
Eagle	18	Gold	18	36
Falcon	18	Nickel	17	35
Flamingo	18	Platinum	17	35
Phoenix	18	Rhodium	17	35
Hummingbird	18	Silver	18	36
Sparrow	15	Titanium	18	33
Godwit	18	Zinc	17	35
Kingfisher	18			18
Total	141		122	263

The study involved Grade 9 and 10 students from Palar Integrated School, a critical stage in academic and personal development. The total population of these students was 823. Using the Raosoff sample size calculator with a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, 263 students were randomly selected. Stratified

proportionate allocation ensured representation from all sections, while a random number generator in Excel maintained fairness and minimized sampling bias (Thomas, 2023).

For the qualitative component, 15 participants were purposively selected, including five students, five parents, and five teachers. Participants were chosen based on accessibility, willingness to participate, and their ability to provide meaningful insight on family support and peer influence (Gill, 2020).

The criteria for participant selection are as follows:

Grade Level. Participants were recruited from various sections of grade 9 and 10 in Palar Integrated School.

Academic Performance. Participants' academic performance was evaluated while choosing responses. This criterion included pupils with diverse academic accomplishments, such as top scorers, moderate performers, and those encountering academic obstacles.

Desire to engage. The individuals who declared their desire to participate in the study's implementation were evaluated. Full permission was secured from the learners and their guardians or parents, assuring their voluntary involvement with the project.

This approach allowed the study to capture a broad perspective on how family support and peer networks influence academic achievement. Interviews with parents and teachers complemented student responses, providing a more complete understanding of these influences.

Instruments

Preparation

Duquesne University (2022) showed that a research technique was used to obtain, measure, and analyze data linked with the issue. It might have included survey replies, parameters, or even inventories. The quantitative procedures of questionnaires comprised the researcher's instruments of choice.

Reliability

Cronbach's α and total amount correlations were done to assess the internal consistency of the Influence of Family Support on Academic Achievement and Peer Networks. The value of Cronbach's α was .867 and .899 respectively, which showed that the questionnaire was a reliable instrument.

To validate the results, the researcher sought a professional practitioner in the industry to confirm the reliability of the instrument. To scrutinize the content of the instrument, the researcher also sought professional help from a licensed statistician, master teacher, and principal under the Department of Education to validate the modified instrument.

Content

The researcher used a researcher-made instrument in this study to gather detailed information from participants. The instrument for the quantitative data collection consists of three parts.

Section 1: Participant Profile and Academic Achievement

Section 2: Self-assessment of Family Support

Section 3: Self-assessment of Peer Networks

The first section of the tool collects information about the participants, including their names, age, gender, and their academic status and achievements. In the second and third section, participants indicate how frequently the experience each item or concept. The scale is as follows.

Table 2

Likert Scale for Self-assessment of Family Support and Peer Networks

		Descriptive Value	Qualitative Equivalent	Interpretation
Family Support	1	1.00-1.74	Never	Very Low Support
Peer Networks		1.00-1.74	Not at All	Negative
Family Support	2	1.75-2.49	Seldom	Low Support
Peer Networks		1.75-2.49	Very Little	Limited
Family Support	3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes	High Support
Peer Networks		2.50-3.24	Somewhat Likely	Positive
Family Support	4	3.25-4.00	Always	Very High Support
Peer Networks		3.25-4.00	To Great Extent	Strongly Positive

Administration

The researcher followed clear procedures to ensure consistency in the survey process. Permission was secured from the Schools Division Office and the participating school, and coordination made with teachers. Respondents from Grades 9 and 10 were selected, and the study's goals and procedures were explained. Since participants were minors, parental consent was obtained.

The researcher created an online survey using Google Forms and administered it in a face-to-face setup to ensure authenticity. Participants were given clear instructions, assured of confidentiality, and encouraged to answer honestly. After data collection, the researcher analyzed the results using descriptive and inferential statistics to examine the relationship between family support, peer networks, and academic achievement.

For the qualitative phase, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with students, parents, and teachers using open-ended guide questions validated by experts for content and face validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

1. Quantitative Phase

Before collecting data, the researcher sought ethical approval from relevant organizations and review boards. Informed consent was obtained from respondents and their parents or guardians, explaining the study's purpose, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw at any time. The researcher selected 263 Grade 9 and 10 students using simple random sampling through a random picker application. Permissions were secured from the division office, school principal, teachers, and parents or guardians.

The researcher explained the study's objectives and procedures to ensure voluntary participation. The online survey was administered in person, with instructions clarified and questions answered before respondents began. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the survey, and all responses were collected while maintaining confidentiality. Finally, the researcher analyzed the quantitative data using descriptive statistics, ensuring clear communication, privacy, and adherence to ethical standards throughout the process.

2. Qualitative Phase

After the participants answered the survey, the researcher asked five representatives from grades 9 and 10 who were interviewed about the influence of family support and peer networks on their academic success. The same ethical considerations were observed. The researcher explained the purpose of the interview and conducted the interview within 30 minutes to ensure that the participants were comfortable. After the student participants, five teachers and five parents were interviewed upon their consent. The respondents for Qualitative data are not included on the actual number of the randomly selected student but came from one focus group.

Data Analysis

For Problem Statement 1, the researcher used descriptive statistics, including frequency and percentage, to determine students' General Weighted Average (GWA). With consent and in compliance with the Data Privacy Act, advisers provided copies of grades for study purposes. This analysis helped the researcher assess students' academic achievement.

For Problem Statements 2 and 3, the researcher calculated weighted means to analyze the data descriptively.

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

For Problem Statement 4, linear regression was used to examine relationships and predict outcomes. Hypotheses were tested by estimating p-values and comparing correlation coefficients to critical values, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

For Problem Statement 5, the researcher used inductive thematic analysis for qualitative data. Interview transcriptions were analyzed, responses color-coded, and keywords identified as codes. The codes were grouped into themes, and actual participant statements were included in the discussion to capture both explicit and underlying insights. This approach allowed a flexible, thorough understanding of emerging patterns without relying on pre-existing frameworks.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part covers the presentation, analysis, and discussion of results of the data gathered following the research problems. Tables were analyzed with the corresponding interpretation of data in the context of the problem raised and the responses of participants. The first part was based on the survey questionnaire, and deals with quantitative analysis. The second part presents the qualitative finding from interviews.

1. The Level of Academic Achievement of Participants

This study examines the level of academic achievement of grade 9 and 10 learners through their general weighted average from previous grading using data from previous grading periods. The following data were collected and tabulated. The researcher requested the grading sheets from advisory class teachers and analyzed the results based on the categories.

Table 3

Academic Achievement of Participants

	Academic Achievement
Valid	263
Missing	0
Mean	3.905
Std. Deviation	0.978
Minimum	1.000
Maximum	5.000

Note: 5 (Outstanding: GWA 90-100); 4 (Very Satisfactory: GWA 85-89); 3 (Satisfactory: GWA 80-84); 2 (Fairly Satisfactory: GWA 75-79); 1 (Did Not Meet Expectation: GWA Below 75)

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics of the academic achievement of the participants represented by their grade weighted average from previous grading period. There are 263 valid responses or data points in the dataset without missing data points. The average academic achievement is approximately 3.91 on a scale from 1 to 5. With the Standard Deviation of 0.978, the grades of the participants suggest that there is moderate variability.

This further implies that most respondents' academic achievement is relatively high, with scores clustering around the upper end of the scale.

Studies have shown that parental involvement, including in providing academic support and fostering a positive home environment, significantly influences students' academic achievement (Basel, 2024). Even in contexts with lower socioeconomic status, increased parental engagement has been linked to improved academic outcomes, suggesting that family support plays a crucial role in students attaining "Very Satisfactory" General Weighted Mean (GWA).

The prevalence of "Very Satisfactory" General Weighted Mean (GWA) among Junior High School students can be attributed to a combination of effective study habits, strong academic motivation and resilience, active parental involvement, and participation in extracurricular activities. These interconnected factors create an environment conducive to academic excellence.

The data reflects a positive trend in academic performance, consistent with national efforts to improve education quality and access. However, the presence of students in the lower performance brackets underscores the need for targeted interventions to support at-risk learners and ensure inclusive academic success.

2. The Level of Family Support that they Receive from Parents or Guardians

Bronfenbrenner's theory emphasizes that a child's development is influenced by multiple layers of environmental systems, with the **microsystem** (e.g., family, school, immediate peers) being the most immediate and impactful. Parental support is a core component of this microsystem, shaping academic, emotional, and social outcomes through daily interactions and expectations.

Table 4

Level of Family Support from their Parents or Guardians

Indicators	Group of Parents or Guardians	Weighted Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. My parents are involved in my academic activities, such as helping with my homework, attending school events, or discussing educational goals.	<i>Outstanding</i>	2.656	0.898	High Level of Support
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.583	1.017	High Level of Support
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.587	1.087	High Level of Support
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	1.947	0.970	Low Level of Support
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	1.333	0.816	Very Low Level of Support
2. I communicate with my family members about my academic progress, challenges, and goals.	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.049	0.889	High Level of Support
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.913	0.904	High Level of Support
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.826	1.018	High Level of Support
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	1.842	0.834	Low Level of Support
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	1.167	0.408	Very Low Level of Support
3. My parents provide resources, such as books, educational	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.713	0.567	Very High Level of Support

materials, or access to technology, to support my learning.	Very Satisfactory	3.730	0.597	Very High Level of Support
	Satisfactory	3.304	1.030	Very High Level of Support
	Fairly Satisfactory	2.526	1.124	High Level of Support
	Needs Improvement	2.000	1.265	Low Level of Support
4. I receive emotional support (listening and understanding, validation, encouragement, empathy, and respect) from my family in relation to my studies.	Outstanding	3.213	0.884	High Level of Support
	Very Satisfactory	3.287	0.944	Very High Level of Support
	Satisfactory	3.174	1.018	High Level of Support
	Fairly Satisfactory	2.263	1.098	Low Level of Support
5. My family members encourage me to set and achieve academic goals.	Outstanding	3.533	0.683	Very High Level of Support
	Very Satisfactory	3.470	0.787	Very High Level of Support
	Satisfactory	3.239	0.848	High Level of Support
	Fairly Satisfactory	2.579	1.121	High Level of Support
6. I have a conducive study environment at home, including a	Outstanding	3.074	0.920	High Level of Support
	Very Satisfactory			
	Satisfactory			
	Fairly Satisfactory			

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

quiet space and necessary resources, facilitated by my family.	Very Satisfactory	2.904	0.927	High Level of Support
	Satisfactory	2.739	1.021	High Level of Support
	Fairly Satisfactory	2.474	1.124	Low Level of Support
	Needs Improvement	1.500	0.837	Very Low Level of Support
7. My family's expectations for my academic performance impact my motivation and effort in school.	Outstanding	3.246	1.023	High Level of Support
	Very Satisfactory	3.104	0.931	High Level of Support
	Satisfactory	2.848	1.095	High Level of Support
	Fairly Satisfactory	2.368	1.065	Low Level of Support
	Needs Improvement	1.667	0.816	Very Low Level of Support
8. My family members are supportive of my participation in extracurricular activities that complement my studies.	Outstanding	3.443	0.739	Very High Level of Support
	Very Satisfactory	3.322	0.854	Very High Level of Support
	Satisfactory	3.000	1.054	High Level of Support
	Fairly Satisfactory	2.368	1.257	Low Level of Support
	Needs Improvement	1.833	1.169	Low Level of Support
9. I seek guidance from my family in making decisions related to my education.	Outstanding	3.213	0.920	High Level of Support
	Very Satisfactory	3.296	0.794	Very High Level of Support

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

	<i>Satisfactory</i>	3.043	1.032	High Level of Support
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.368	1.165	High Level of Support
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	1.667	0.816	Very Low Level of Support
10. The support I receive from my family influence my overall academic achievement and well-being.	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.582	0.811	Very High Level of Support
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	3.409	0.878	Very High Level of Support
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	3.087	1.007	High Level of Support
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.579	0.838	High Level of Support
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.167	0.983	Low Level of Support
	Overall	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.272	0.294
<i>Very Satisfactory</i>		3.201		High Level of Support
<i>Satisfactory</i>		2.984		High Level of Support
<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>		2.331		Low Level of Support
<i>Needs Improvement</i>		1.733		Very Low Level of Support

Overall, the results show that students generally perceive a high level of family support, though the degree of involvement varies across academic performance groups.

For most students, parents provide strong material and emotional support, such as offering educational resources, encouragement, and guidance. The highest-rated aspect across groups was the provision of learning materials and technology, showing parents' commitment to their children's education. However, direct involvement—like helping with homework or attending school activities—was rated lower, likely due to time constraints, limited understanding of the curriculum, or other responsibilities.

Students with very satisfactory performance reported consistent parental engagement, both emotional and material. Those in the satisfactory group still perceived strong encouragement but less hands-on participation. In contrast, fairly satisfactory and needs improvement groups revealed weaker family involvement,

especially in communication, emotional support, and study environment—factors closely linked to lower academic motivation and achievement.

These findings echo previous studies (Wong, 2008; Sengonul, 2022; Contreras, 2024) emphasizing that emotional bonding and meaningful parental interaction are key to student success. In line with Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, family remains a crucial microsystem influencing learners' academic and emotional growth.

Strengthening school-home collaboration through initiatives like the Homeroom Parent-Teacher Program can help bridge gaps in involvement, equip parents with practical strategies, and ensure that every learner—regardless of background—receives the support they need to thrive academically and personally.

3. Extent of Learners' Peer Networks and Interaction and their Academic Achievement

Table 5

Extent of Learners' Peer Networks and Interaction and their Academic Achievement

Indicators	Group of Students	Weighted Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I do interact with my peers outside of formal class settings.	<i>Outstanding</i>	2.893	0.925	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.748	0.926	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.348	0.849	Limited
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.158	0.834	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.500	0.837	Positive
2. I engage in collaborative learning activities with my peers, such as group projects or study sessions.	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.418	0.870	Strongly Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	3.357	0.910	Strongly Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	3.000	0.989	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.421	0.902	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.167	0.408	Limited
3. I exchange academic information or resources with my peers to enhance my understanding of course materials.	<i>Outstanding</i>	2.861	0.846	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.713	0.934	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.652	0.924	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.263	0.872	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.000	1.265	Limited
4. I feel supported by my peers in academic matters, such as seeking	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.090	0.872	Positive

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

help or discussing academic challenges.	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.939	0.901	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.674	1.156	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.474	1.124	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.333	1.033	Limited
5. I participate in any formal or informal study groups with my peers.	<i>Outstanding</i>	2.902	1.071	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.730	1.012	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.609	0.930	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.579	0.902	Positive
6. The motivation and academic performance of my peers influence my own motivation and performance.	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.167	1.169	Limited
	<i>Outstanding</i>	2.934	0.934	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.983	0.936	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.565	0.981	Positive
7. I seek feedback from my peers on my academic work, and I value such feedback.	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.316	0.946	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.333	0.816	Limited
	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.049	0.952	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.835	0.964	Positive
8. I make sure that I have diverse peer network in terms of academic interests, backgrounds, and perspectives.	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.674	0.871	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.474	0.841	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.333	1.366	Limited
	<i>Outstanding</i>	2.959	0.876	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.922	0.929	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.674	0.944	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.158	0.834	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.000	1.265	Limited

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

9. I use social media platforms to connect with my peers for academic discussions or sharing educational resources.	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.230	0.943	Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	3.104	1.003	Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.870	0.957	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.368	0.831	Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.333	1.033	Limited
10. I acknowledge the importance of peer recognition and acknowledgment in my peer network for academic achievements or contributions to learning.	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.508	0.741	Strongly Positive
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	3.409	0.847	Strongly Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	3.065	0.929	Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.579	0.961	Positive
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.667	0.816	Positive
Overall	<i>Outstanding</i>	3.084		<i>Positive</i>
	<i>Very Satisfactory</i>	2.973		Positive
	<i>Satisfactory</i>	2.713		Positive
	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>	2.378		Limited
	<i>Needs Improvement</i>	2.283		Limited

Results show that peer interactions play a crucial role in academic performance, with stronger engagement linked to higher achievement.

Students with outstanding and very satisfactory performance reported positive peer relationships, active collaboration, and frequent academic discussions. They often engage in study groups, share learning materials, and recognize each other's achievements, showing that peer support enhances motivation and academic engagement. These findings echo Shao et al. (2024) and Yu et al. (2023), who found that positive peer influence boosts learning motivation and performance.

In the satisfactory group, students still show a positive but moderate level of peer interaction. They value peer recognition and group work but engage less outside the classroom or through social media. Peer collaboration exists but is not yet a strong learning habit.

Among fairly satisfactory and needs improvement students, peer interaction is limited, especially in informal and academic support contexts. These students rarely collaborate or seek peer feedback, and many underuse digital tools for learning. The lack of diverse and supportive peer connections may hinder motivation, confidence, and academic growth.

Overall, the study highlights that strong, supportive, and diverse peer networks foster academic success and emotional resilience. Schools can strengthen peer collaboration through structured study groups, peer mentoring, and digital learning communities to help students at all performance levels thrive.

4. Significant Relationship of family Support and Peer Networks on the Academic Achievement of Learners

A regression analysis was used for the study to quantify the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables. The Model Summary from the regression analysis assessing the relationship between predictors (likely family support, peer influence, etc.) and academic achievement is presented in Table 6. The model can be used to predict academic outcomes based on levels of parental support and peer influence, which is useful for educational planning and interventions.

Table 6

Significant Relationship of Family Support and Peer Networks with Academic Achievement

Model Summary – Academic Achievement

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	RMSE
M ₁	0.661	0.438	0.271	0.835

Note. M₁ includes FS 1, FS 2, FS 3, FS 4, FS 5, FS 6, FS 7, FS 8, FS 9, FS 10, PN 1, PN 2, PN 3, PN 4, PN 5, PN 6, PN 7, PN8, PN 9, PN 10

The model includes meaningful predictors (i.e., family support, peer networks) and shows moderate predictive power. Moderate positive correlation (0.661) — as predictors increase, academic achievement tends to increase. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Family support provides the foundational stability and motivation learners need. It likely contributes significantly to the positive R² value (0.438), indicating that students with strong family support tend to perform better academically. The Model's adjusted R² (0.271) suggests that after accounting for model complexity, about 27.1% of the variance is still explained, indicating a moderate model fit. On the other hand, peer networks can either enhance or hinder academic performance. In the Model, this variable likely explains part of the variance in academic outcomes, especially when peer influence is constructive. While both factors are important, family support plays a more substantial role in predicting academic success in this model.

Based on the results, the family support and peer networks have a major influence on the learners' welfare. Data shows that these factors have a significant relationship in the students' life journey, supported by statistical proof contribute their impact. The combination of the two variables highlighting the relation of their social relationships in nurturing the adaptability and personal development. As mentioned by Jamison et. al (2022) emphasize the peer-led family support programs have a positive impact on parental obligation and reduced adolescents' psychological problems, highlighting the combined influence of family and peer support pillar.

Table 7

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
M ₁	Regression	109.666	60	1.828	2.619	< .001
	Residual	140.958	202	0.698		
	Total	250.624	262			

Note. M₁ includes FS 1, FS 2, FS 3, FS 4, FS 5, FS 6, FS 7, FS 8, FS 9, FS 10, PN 1, PN 2, PN 3, PN 4, PN 5, PN 6, PN 7, PN8, PN 9, PN 10

The ANOVA F-test result (F = 2.619, p < .001) confirms that the model significantly predicts academic achievement. This means that family support and peer networks, as a group, have a real and measurable impact on students' academic performance.

The assumption tests performed for the model include normality, linearity, homoscedasticity, and multicollinearity. The data suggests that the residuals are approximately normally distributed. This supports the assumption that the errors in the regression model are normally distributed. The regression results are likely valid, at least in terms of the normality assumption. The linearity assumption appears to be satisfied. The

homoscedasticity assumption also appears to be met with the spread of residuals appear to be fairly consistent across the range of predicted values. Finally, as to multicollinearity, VIF values range from 1.197 to 1.440, and Tolerance values range from 0.694 to 0.835 for the variables where these metrics are reported. All VIF values are well below 5, and all Tolerance values are well above 0.1. This means there is no serious multicollinearity among the predictors in the regression model. The regression model satisfies the assumption of no multicollinearity, supporting the validity of the analysis.

To support the quantitative data, interviews were collected to have a deeper understanding about the significant relationship of family and peer support with the academic achievement of learners to draw an input to strengthened existing Parent-Teacher Program in Palar Integrated School.

5. Results of Interviews on the Influence of Family and Peer Networks on the Academic Achievement of Learners

There were fifteen (15) respondents in the interview which include five (5) parents, five (5) students and five (5) teachers to elicit their responses on the influence of family support and peer networks on the academic achievement of learners. The table below shows the participants responses that were arranged to come up with themes.

Table 8

Participants Perception on Family and Peer Support on the Academic Achievement of Learners

Theme	Codes (keywords)	Sample Statement	Participant
Emotional, Financial and Motivational Support	Support, "tulong", positive	"The support of the family is very crucial, if the learners are experiencing stress and the parents did not know about the child's problem, there is a tendency that the student performance becomes low."	Teacher
		"Financially, binibigay nila ang kailangan ko sa school, at emotionally parang na-inspire nila ako."	Student
		"Naibigay ko ang pinansyal at emosyonal na suporta na hirap ako at nagawa ko."	Parent
		"Binigyan ko sila ng oras para mag-aral. Ang pinaka magandang payo ko ay ang lagging magpasalamat sa Diyos."	Parent
		"Kung pinababayaan ko yan siguro ay addicted na rin sa pagvavape o paninigarilyo"	Parent
Limited Emotional Engagement	"hindi masyado"	"More on financial at hindi sila masyadong nakatutok sa emotional."	Student
	"walang suporta"	"Kapag hindi talaga sila sinusuportahan ng kanilang mga magulang, mas bumaba ang kanilang mga grado"	Teacher
	"wala ang magulang"		
Parental Involvement in School Activities	"nandyan", "involved"	"Kapag may project ang mga bata, minsan nandyan ang mga magulang para bihisang ang mga anak nila, naaappreciate sila ng mga bata."	Teacher
Socioeconomic Challenges	"mahirap", "mahina"	"Most of the cases, mahina ang academic performance dahil sa kanilang katayuan sa buhay..hindi sila kumukuha ng baon, kaya hindi na lang sila pumasok sa paaralan."	Teacher

Communication and Presence	"kamustahin", "communication", open	"So dapat hindi lang financial support, pero dapat nandyan ang presensya nila para kamustahin ang mga nangyayari sa loob at labas ng paaralan."	Teacher
Peer-Assisted Learning and		"Pagdating sa mga kasamahan....nagtutulungan sa mga takdang-aralin ...nabibigyan rin ng sapat na mga marka."	Teacher
Positive Influence	Teamwork, tulongan, kasamahan	"Tinutulungan nila ako kapag nahihirapan ako...sila rin ang nagmomotivate sa akin minsan dahil na pepressure ako."	Student
Peer Pressure and Risk Behaviors	Bully, pressure, Bl, vices, suicide	"Kapag wala sila at may sakit, tinutulungan siya at ng kanyang mga kaibigan sa kanyang mga aralin." "Ginawa ko siyang officer, tinabi ko siya sa mga makukulitnaging kaibigan niya na sila...napabayaang niya ang kanyang pag-aaral." "May dalawang klase akong kaibigan ...ang iba ay masamang impluwensya, gaya ng pag-iinom ng alak at paninigarilyo."	Teacher Parent
		"Noong grade eight ako, bumaba ang grades ko..ilang beses na ako nag attempt na magpakamatay...dahil sa bullying."	Student

The qualitative findings revealed that family and peer support play a significant role in shaping learners' academic achievement at Palar Integrated School.

Parents emphasized three main forms of support—financial, emotional, and parental guidance—as essential to their children's academic success. Financial support ensures that students have access to learning materials and other necessities, while emotional and spiritual guidance helps build confidence, discipline, and motivation (Olusegun, 2024; Nimmi et al., 2021; Shroff et al., 2023). Parents observed that when these supports are present, their children's academic performance improves. However, they also expressed concern about negative peer influences, such as exposure to vices and inappropriate behavior, which often lead to academic decline.

From the students' perspective, financial and emotional support from their families greatly motivates them to study and persevere. Encouragement and reassurance reduce academic stress and strengthen resilience (Lobo, 2024). Nevertheless, some students reported insufficient emotional support at home, which affected their confidence and well-being, consistent with OECD (2024) findings that lack of emotional support can lead to poor coping mechanisms. Students also highlighted the dual nature of peer influence—positive peers encourage collaboration and academic growth, while negative peers contribute to distractions, bad habits, and even emotional distress.

Teachers supported these observations, noting that students who receive consistent family support and engage in positive peer interactions tend to perform better academically. Parental involvement, motivation, and financial assistance were identified as strong predictors of achievement, while lack of family engagement and exposure to negative peer groups often result in lower performance and behavioral challenges.

Overall, the findings indicate that strong family engagement and positive peer networks foster academic motivation, confidence, and achievement. In contrast, emotional neglect and negative peer influence hinder students' learning and personal growth. These results align with Ratumbuisang et al. (2024) and Nicolas (2022), who emphasized that both parental support and peer environment significantly shape learners' academic outcomes. The study underscores the importance of strengthening home-school collaboration and peer support programs to promote holistic student development and academic success.

Integrated Result of the Study

This table presents the integrated results of the study Influence of Family Support and Peer Networks on Academic Achievements of Learners, with the aim of generating practical inputs for a Strengthened Homeroom Parent- Teacher Program. The findings highlight how combined effects of Parental involvement and peer interactions shape learners' academic performance, particularly among Junior High School Students. By analyzing the relationship between these external support systems and academic outcomes, the study provides evidence – based insights to enhance school- home collaboration and promote learner success.

Table 9

Quantitative-Qualitative Data Integration

SOP's	Area of Enrichment	Emerging Themes	Program Implications
1. What is the level of academic achievement of the participants?	-Tutorial sessions or differentiated instruction in low -performing subjects. -Students belonging to below average groups may require more parental support and peer networks.		The school should be able to address the needs of its learners especially those who are underperforming through prompt feedback.
2. What is the participants' perceived level of family support?	-Reinforce parental support for low performing students -Parental involvement in both material and motivational forms aligning with Bronfenbrenner's view that consistent, meaningful interactions are valuable for holistic development	-Limited Emotional engagement of Parents -Lack of Support leading to poor performance -Socioeconomic Challenges -Communication and Presence	Encourage school- family partnerships to bridge gaps between home and school environments, fostering consistent support across settings.
3. What is the extent of peer networks and interactions of the respondents?	-Outstanding students benefit from rich, supportive, and diverse peer networks -Need for interventions to build peer support systems -Low-performing groups indicate social and academic isolation	-Negative Peer Influence and Behavioral Issues -Peer Pressure and Risk Behaviors	-The school should help students manage peer pressure and build healthy relationships -The school must be able to communicate to the parents the guidance and anti- bullying programs. -Monitoring of risky behavior must be Institutionalized
4. Do levels of family support and peer networks have a significant relationship on the academic achievement	-Family support plays a more substantial role in predicting academic success in the model.	-All three groups agree that family support especially emotional and financial—is empirical to academic success. -While peers can be a source of motivation	-Schools can host parent-teacher workshops to teach parents how to increase parental involvement. -Academic achievement is deeply influenced by

World Education Connect
Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
 Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
 Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
 DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

of Junior High School Learners?

and academic help, they can also introduce distractions and harmful behaviors. -Parents and teachers both stress the importance of active monitoring and communication to mitigate negative peer influence.

both family and peer environment. Therefore, school programs must adopt a comprehensive community-based approach that integrates family engagement and positive peer development into -the core of educational planning and support services. This approach not only strengthens academic performance but also promotes holistic growth among Junior High School Learners.

5. How are family support and peer networks and interaction practices experienced participants in line with their academic achievements ?

-Strengthening Holistic Home- School Collaboration
 -Strengthening Feedback Mechanism through monthly check-ins, meetings and digital tools
 -Enhancing Learning Action Cells for Parents
 -Reinforcement of the Home- School Connection Performance Tasks

-Emotional, Financial and Motivational Support
 -Limited Emotional Engagement
 -Parental Involvement in School Activities
 -Socioeconomic Challenges
 -Communication and Presence
 -Peer-Assisted Learning and
 -Positive Influence
 -Peer Pressure and Risk Behaviors

The school should strengthen its collaboration with the parents/ guardians through learning sessions on positive discipline, mental health awareness, and motivational parenting especially for this generation of learners.

6. Proposed Strengthened Parent-Teacher Program

“Kasama sa Pagtataguyod sa Edukasyon: A Strengthened Parent-Teacher Program”

Rationale:

Based on the results of the study, academic achievement of learners is significantly influenced by their environment, particularly with their family and peer networks. While this connection can help as sources of encouragement, they can also add to academic struggles when negative influences arise, such as lack of parental support, domestic problems, or peer pressure leading to distractions and poor academic habits. With the program implications listed in the table, the researcher designed the following program to strengthen the enabling contributions of the significant components of a student's immediate environment referred to as the microsystem in the Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory, which includes the school, the home, and peer networks.

Objectives:

1. To be able to provide timely and meaningful feedback to parents about their children's academic achievement and social interactions at school (*Components 1, 2 and 3*).
2. To be able to create learning opportunities for parents how to help students manage peer pressure and build healthy relationships including positive discipline, mental health awareness, and motivational parenting especially for this generation of learners (*Components 1, 2 and 3*).
3. To be able to collaborate with parents on how to better monitor risky behavior among students (*Component 1, 2 and 3*).

Legal Basis:

- DepEd Order No. 83, s. 2012 (Implementing Guidelines on the Parent-Teachers Association (PTA) Operations in Schools)
- Republic Act No. 10361 (Parent Effectiveness Service Program Act)

Description of the Program:

The "**Kasama sa Pagtataguyod sa Edukasyon: A Strengthened Parent-Teacher Program**" aims to strengthen collaboration between parents and teachers. When both parties work together it will minimize the risks of academic failure due to negative influences. Through driven engagement, counseling, and educational training, this program will empower parents or guardians to take an active role in their child's academic journey.

Table 10

Program Components

Components	Description	Reference in the Study Results
1. Feedback Mechanism - Quarterly PTA meetings - Monthly Check-ins - PTA Viber/FB Group	Aside from the quarterly PTA meetings that includes showcasing of students' outputs and distribution of report cards, advisory teacher may also use monthly check-in slips to provide feedback on the students' performance. The check-in slips will be sent to the parent concerned.	-Parents and teachers both stress the importance of active monitoring and communication to mitigate negative peer influence. -Reinforce parental support for low performing students
2. Learning Action Cells for Parents - Quarterly learning sessions	Parents will be given quarterly learning sessions that will coincide with the quarterly PTA meetings. The sessions may be in a form of video clips, short talk, or group sharing on topics about the programs of the school, positive discipline, mental health, managing stress and peer pressure in students, among others. This will emphasize the role that they have in their children's development.	Family support plays a more substantial role in predicting academic success in the regression model.
3. Home- School Connection Performance Tasks	Students will be assigned a performance task in any subject that will require collaboration with their parents/guardian.	-Parental involvement in both material and motivational forms is crucial for students' development. -Low-performing groups indicate social and academic isolation.

-Communication and Presence.

Program Action Plan

The program will run for one academic year (with the possibility of extension based on the evaluation results). This includes four phases, each phase has activities, persons involve and timeline to ensure effective monitoring and sustainability.

Table 11

Action Plan for "Kasama sa Pagtataguyod sa Edukasyon: A Strengthened Parent-Teacher Program"

PHASES	ACTION NEEDED	PERSONS RESPONSIBLE	TIMELINE
Phase 1: Planning and Preparation <i>Adapting a digital communication tool - online and offline digital platform (e.g., dedicated app, social media groups, websites, or school portal)</i>	-Organize and develop a program materials, schedules, and communication channels -Digital platform can host announcements, academic progress updates, event calendars, and allow for direct, easy communication between both parties	School Heads, Teachers, LGU, parents and other stakeholders	One month (before opening of class)
Phase 2: Orientation of the Program	-Orientation on program objectives, expectations, and roles of educators, parents, and stakeholders.	School Heads, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders	One month (after opening of class)
Phase 3: Program Implementation	-Regular monthly meetings to discuss student progress and challenges and sharing of the best practices in parental support. -Organizing virtual feedback sessions, surveys, and one-on-one meetings that allow for continuous engagement.	School Heads, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders	July to March
Phase 4: Recognition and Refinement of Program	-Acknowledge active parent and teacher participants and propose plans for program continuation or enhancement in the next academic year.	School Heads, Teachers, LGU, parents and other stakeholders	Year-end

Visual Presentation of the Parent-Teacher Program

figure 3

This program differs from traditional PTAs by directly addressing the negative effects of family support and peer networks on student achievement. Unlike standard programs that focus mainly on school involvement, it

adopts a holistic approach tailored to students' needs based on the study's findings. It combines parent education, peer influence management, and ongoing teacher collaboration.

Parent education provides learning sessions that equip parents with strategies to support their children academically and emotionally, manage peer influence, and create a positive learning environment. Peer influence management includes student counseling and tutoring to help resist negative peer pressure. Continuous parent-teacher collaboration ensures regular engagement through monthly discussions, monitoring of academic progress, and a dedicated help desk for timely interventions.

The program also partners with community stakeholders such as mental health professionals, local leaders, TESDA, NGOs, and youth organizations to strengthen student support systems. Active participants are recognized, reinforcing home-school collaboration and creating a stronger, supportive environment for academic success.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. These results highlight a generally positive academic trend, with room for targeted support for the small group of learners who are struggling.
2. Students belonging to groups with above average performance are more likely to have a very high level of family support. They have high level of family support in terms of their participation in extracurricular activities, receive emotional support, have a conducive study environment at home, open communication, parental involvement in academic works.
3. Depending on the categories of academic achievement, the lower the performance of the students, the more evident they are to become socially and academically isolated.
4. The model presented means that family support and peer networks, as a group, have a real and measurable impact on students' academic performance.
5. The qualitative data (from students, parents, and teachers) and the statistical results both highlight the importance of emotional, financial, and social support. Peer influence can be both constructive (e.g., collaborative learning) and destructive (e.g., vices, distractions). It must be noted however that this conclusion applies only to contexts similar to the one where the study was conducted since other latent factors other than those mentioned in the scope were not integrated in the analysis.

Recommendations:

1. Teachers should be able to address the needs of its learners especially those who are underperforming through timely feedback.
2. Parents should be able to work on building stronger emotional support to learners especially when peer networks are becoming detrimental. An open communication line with their children is highly recommended.
3. School-family partnerships to bridge gaps between home and school environments must be reinforced by including program components in the parent-teacher conferences that provides avenue for feedback, learning sessions, and home-school connections.
4. The school and its administrators must be able to communicate to the parents the guidance and anti-bullying programs.
5. The Department of Education should strengthen its policies and procedures in monitoring of risky behavior.
6. Based on the study, the researcher recommends researcher-made strengthened Parent- Teacher Program that cater to the importance of family support and peer networks and strengthen the positive impact on the academic achievement of learners. It is important to likewise consider that the perceived effects of the program may only be predicted in contexts like the one where the study was conducted since other latent factors other than those mentioned in the scope were not integrated in the analysis.
7. Future research including socio-economic status and parental communication styles as variables is recommended. Moreover, a study to evaluate the effects of the proposed program may also be

undertaken. Finally, use of other data source such as anecdotal records and counselling notes supporting a more longitudinal study could add depth to the analysis of parental support and peer networks

REFERENCES

- Agostinelli, F., Doepke, M., Sorrenti, G., & Zilibotti, F. (2022). When the great equalizer shuts down: Schools, peers, and parents in pandemic times. *Journal of Public Economics*, 206, 104574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2021.104574>
- Ahmad Bhat, R. (2023). The Impact of Technology Integration on Student Learning Outcomes: A Comparative Study. *International Journal of Social Science Educational Economics Agriculture Research and Technology (IJSET)*, 2(9), 592–596. <https://doi.org/10.54443/ijset.v2i9.218>
- American Psychological Association. (2022). *Speaking of Psychology: Why Gen Z is feeling so stressed*. Apa.org. <https://www.apa.org/news/podcasts/speaking-of-psychology/gen-z-stress>
- Balayar, B. B., & Langlais, M. R. (2021). Parental Support, Learning Performance, and Socioemotional Development of Children and Teenagers During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *The Family Journal*, 106648072110524. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10664807211052496>
- Bautista, J. (2023, December 11). 1 in 3 Filipino students bullied in school – Pisa study. INQUIRER.net. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1873526/1-in-3-filipino-students-bullied-in-school-pisa-study>
- Berthelon, M., Bettinger, E., Kruger, D. I., & Montecinos-Pearce, A. (2019). The Structure of Peers: The Impact of Peer Networks on Academic Achievement. *Research in Higher Education*, 60(7), 931–959. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-018-09543-7>
- Bloom, S. (2022, July 14). *Mental Health in Schools: Moving Stigma Out in the Open*. Behavioral Health News. <https://behavioralhealthnews.org/mental-health-in-schools-moving-stigma-out-in-the-open/>
- Board, C. K. (2022). *Analyzing the Academic Achievement of Secondary Virtual Learners during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Mixed Methods Case Study - ProQuest*. Wwww.proquest.com. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/faf8075028212753efe97a77a5d577cd/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Brouwer, J., de Matos Fernandes, C. A., Steglich, C. E. G., Jansen, E. P. W. A., Hofman, W. H. A., & Flache, A. (2022). The development of peer networks and academic performance in learning communities in higher education. *Learning and Instruction*, 80, 101603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2022.101603>
- Brouwer, J., & Engels, M. C. (2021). The role of prosocial attitudes and academic achievement in peer networks in higher education. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-020-00526-w>
- Bucăța, G. (2023). Challenges at the Educational Level in the Teaching and Training of Generation "Z." *Revista Academiei Forțelor Terestre*, 28(4), 265–276. <https://doi.org/10.2478/raft-2023-0031>
- Bujang MA, Omar ED, Baharum NA. A Review on Sample Size Determination for Cronbach's Alpha Test: A Simple Guide for Researchers. *Malays J Med Sci*. 2018 Nov;25(6):85-99. doi: 10.21315/mjms2018.25.6.9. Epub 2018 Dec 28. PMID: 30914882; PMCID: PMC6422571.
- Burgess, B. (2021). *Engaging and Educating Gen Z*. <https://getzproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Educating-and-Engaging-Generation-Z-Beth-Burgess.pdf>
- Carredo, G., Delgado, M. J., Dragas, F., Rasco, A. M., & Derasin, L. M. (2022). Effect of Learners' Level of Motivation in Developing Their Study Habits Amid the Pandemic. *International Journal of Science and Management Studies (IJSMS)*, 64–72. <https://doi.org/10.51386/25815946/ijms-v5i4p107>
- David, D., Situmorang, B., Mini, R., & Salim, A. (2020). The Effects of Authoritative Paternal- Maternal Parenting Styles on Career Decision Self-Efficacy of Gen Z Adolescents: Thinking Styles as Mediators. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*. Wwww.ijcc.net, 13(10), 2020. https://www.ijcc.net/images/vol_13/Iss_10/131011_Situmorang_2020_E_R.pdf
- Department of Education. (2019, December 4). *Statement on the Philippines' ranking in the 2018 PISA results | Department of Education*. Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/12/04/statement-on-the-philippines-ranking-in-the-2018-pisa-results/>
- Garnham, C. (2022, May 13). *The Gen Z Mental Health wave - what is causing the surge?* HealthMatch. <https://healthmatch.io/blog/the-gen-z-mental-health-wave-what-is-causing-the-surge>

- Gutierrez Albarico, A., Perez Blas, R., Palomo Cruz, A., & Mendoza Enriquez, G. (2023). FACTORS AFFECTING SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS POOR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE. *Fully Refereed International Journal () @International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering*, 5565, 2582– 5208. <https://doi.org/10.56726/IRJMETS37089>
- Guy-Evans, O. (2022, November 3). *Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory*. SimplyPsychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/Bronfenbrenner.html#The-Five-Ecological-Systems>
- Jihan, J., Mamonto, S., Fatmawati, E., Darmo, I. S., & Muchtar, M. (2023). Exploring the Impact of Post-Pandemic Learning Strategies on University Students' Engagement and Academic Achievement. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 15(3), 3017–3027. <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v15i3.3742>
- Kirsch, C., & Vaiouli, P. (2023). Students' perspectives on their academic achievement during the Covid-19 pandemic: Learner autonomy, school satisfaction and adult support. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 7(1), 100433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100433>
- Koele, I. J., Blankenstein, N. E., Güröğlü, B., Schreuders, E., & van Duijvenvoorde, A. C. K. (2023, March 13). *Adolescents' Friendship Quality, Internalizing Problems, and Academic Achievement during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Longitudinal Study*. www.researchsquare.com. <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-2653418/v1>
- Lo, K. W. K., Ngai, G., Chan, S. C. F., & Kwan, K. (2022). How Students' Motivation and Learning Experience Affect Their Service-Learning Outcomes: A Structural Equation Modeling Analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.825902>
- Manila Bulletin. (2019, September 9). *HP study shows Filipino millennial parents want their kids "future-proof."* Manila Bulletin. https://mb.com.ph/2019/09/09/hp-study-shows-filipino-millennial-parents-want-their-kids-future-proof/#google_vignette
- Maimad, M. T., Dupa, J. P., & Villegas, J. P. (2023). Parental Involvement and Academic Achievement: Keys to Translating No Poverty and Quality Education SDGs in Philippine Peripheral Communities. *Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability*, 25(2), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.2478/jtes-2023-0017>
- Martin, A. J., Collie, R. J., & Nagy, R. P. (2021, August 21). *Students who are more adaptable do best in remote learning – and it's a skill we can teach*. The Conversation. <https://theconversation.com/students-who-are-more-adaptable-do-best-in-remote-learning-and-its-a-skill-we-can-teach-165003>
- Mau Kasi, Y. E., Suparno, S., & Asib, A. (2021). Parents' Involvement in Students' Academic Achievement in Distance Learning Process During the Pandemic of Covid-19. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, 2(1), 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.47175/rielsj.v2i1.202>
- Meşe, E., & Sevilen, Ç. (2021). Factors influencing EFL students' motivation in online learning: A qualitative case study. *Journal of Educational Technology & Online Learning*, 4(1), 11–22. <https://doi.org/10.31681/jetol>
- Motz, B. A., Quick, J. D., Wernert, J. A., & Miles, T. A. (2021). A Pandemic of Busywork: Increased Online Coursework Following the Transition to Remote Instruction Is Associated with Reduced Academic Achievement. *Online Learning*, 25(1), 70–85. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1287108>
- Nurhopipah, A., Nuraida, I., & Suhaman, J. (2021). Exploring Indirect Aspects in Motivation and Academic Achievement During The Pandemic. *Journal of Education, Teaching and Learning*, 6(2), 163–168. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/219953/>
- Schwieger, D., & Ladwig, C. (2018). Reaching and Retaining the Next Generation: Adapting to the Expectations of Gen Z in the Classroom. *Information Systems Education Journal (ISEDJ)*, 3, 16. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1179303.pdf>
- Services, M. S. T. (2023, August 10). *Promoting Mental Health Awareness in Schools: Breaking the Stigma*. [Info.mstservices.com](http://info.mstservices.com). <https://info.mstservices.com/blog/mental-health-awareness-in-schools>
- Sharma, S., Singh, S., & Kumar, N. (2023). The New Millennium Family Functioning and Health of Generation Z: From a Socioconstructivist Perspective. *Journal of Indian Association for Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 097313422311614. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09731342231161473>
- Steinmayr, R., Weidinger, A. F., Schwinger, M., & Spinath, B. (2019). The Importance of Students' Motivation for Their Academic Achievement – Replicating and Extending Previous Findings. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10(1730). ncbi. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01730>

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), pp.216-243 International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

- Vignery, K., & Laurier, W. (2020). Achievement in student peer networks: A study of the selection process, peer effects and student centrality. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 101499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2019.101499>
- Wei, Z. (2023). Navigating Digital Learning Landscapes: Unveiling the Interplay Between Learning Behaviors, Digital Literacy, and Educational Outcomes. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01522-3>
- Zafirah, N., Tumanggor, R. O., & Tasdin, W. (2021, August 8). *Family Support and Learning Achievement in Junior High School Students During the Covid-19 Pandemic*. www.atlantis-press.com; Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210805.04>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17668140

